

Illiteracy and Its Measures to Eradicate It

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Abstract: -

One of the biggest issues that exists everywhere in the world is illiteracy. The fundamental societal issues of poverty, illiteracy, and unemployment have a negative impact on many developing nations, including India. The biggest obstacle in the way of development is these issues. Many people, communities, and socioeconomic groups are unable to obtain the bare minimum of a level of living or education. Poverty is the main consequence of illiteracy in India.

Both developed and emerging nations struggle with poverty. When a person's income falls below a given threshold, they are declared to be in poverty. An individual is said to be living in poverty when he or she is unable to meet basic needs such as proper nutrition, shelter, clothes, healthcare, and education. This research article emphasises the strong link between poverty and illiteracy and also discusses solutions to the illiteracy problem.

Keywords: poverty, illiteracy, problems, measures.

Introduction: -

[" Literacy is a bridge from misery to hope. It is a tool for daily life in modern society. It is a bulwork against poverty and a building block of development, an essential compliment to investments in roads, dams, clinics and factories. Literacy is finally the road to human progress

and the means through which every man, woman and child can realise his or her full potential. "

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India is a nation with many different communities, races, religions, and cultures. Every religion on the Indian subcontinent has its own customs, traditions, race, caste, and political democracy, making it unique in the world. The issue of illiteracy is one of the biggest issues that India is now dealing with. When someone are unable to read, write, or answer mathematical problems, they are said to be illiterate. They become uninformed of the crucial regions as a result of their illiteracy. In order to have an effective and productive life, they are unable to grow their talents and abilities, communicate effectively, and overcome obstacles. Therefore, it is essential to address the issue of illiteracy, and everyone, regardless of origin or rank, should recognise the value of education.

Illiteracy is a societal issue that affects people when they are unable to read and write or when they have difficulties using their basic literacy abilities, such as reading, writing, and so on. The social issue of illiteracy exposes people to a variety of challenges and tough circumstances.

They are unable to conduct banking activities, such as withdrawing and depositing money, and in certain situations, they are unable to distinguish between appropriate and inappropriate variables. They are also unable to make purchases of a variety of goods from the market.

Education is a tool that makes a significant contribution to the dissemination of knowledge about academic subjects as well as the generation of knowledge among people about how to develop into moral beings and useful members of society. India after independence has an intrinsic

ailment called illiteracy. After gaining freedom, we discovered that the biggest barrier to our development is our illiteracy. It is really unfortunate that the nation that was viewed as the model for other nations has a high proportion of illiteracy. The majority of India's rural areas are illiterate. Poverty, a lack of high-quality education, the illiteracy of women, and other factors are just a few of the causes of illiteracy in India. In the age of globalisation, the issue of illiteracy persists as a societal and global concern, impeding development efforts. It hinders a person's entire growth at the individual level. It makes it difficult for parents to educate their kids and, more importantly, it causes their lack of self-worth, which breeds loneliness. Society as a whole struggles to function efficiently in the knowledge-driven environment.

Causes of illiteracy: -

In India, the issue of illiteracy affects everyone in every community throughout the nation. This is a roadblock to the advancement of people, communities, and the country as a whole. Compared to metropolitan communities, illiteracy rates are higher among the population in rural areas. Children are the nation's future citizens. Therefore, parents should prioritise giving their children an education. They ought to be inspired to enrol in academic programmes.

1. **Discrimination against girls:-** In a few country networks, male youngsters are resources. They will contribute in advancing prosperity of their families gave they are given chances to do as such. Then again, young ladies are viewed as the liabilities. They are prepared from the phase of youth with regards to execution of family obligations and dealing with needs and prerequisites of relatives. They are deterred from obtaining of

instruction. The explanation being, it is accepted that in their conjugal homes they won't procure the valuable chances to utilize training in any way. Funds are put something aside for their marriage instead of expenditure on procurement of schooling. Subsequently, there is pervasiveness of the unfair treatment against young ladies regarding training.

2. **Financial problems:** - Individuals has to spend money on additional expenses such as textbooks, backpacks, stationery, uniforms, and other study supplies in order to acquire an education. These are thought to be extremely important for achieving educational objectives. When a person has financial difficulties and is unable to cover the costs of getting an education, they are unable to continue their education. The people are unable to increase their knowledge and comprehension using cutting-edge, inventive, and scientific techniques. Therefore, a major contributor to illiteracy is financial difficulties.
3. **Lack of infrastructure, amenities and facilities:** - When suitable infrastructure, amenities, and facilities are provided, all employees of educational institutions feel at ease in their working environment. Additionally, they may focus on their work in a well-organized manner. Schools in remote areas lack infrastructure, services, and facilities. Teachers and pupils thus feel uneasy on the school campus. These facilities and amenities include things like access to clean water for drinking, good sanitation, toilets, technology, playgrounds, and libraries. The children are forced to sit on the floor in the classrooms since there isn't enough furniture there.

4. **Problem of illiteracy in parents:** - Many parents who lack literacy do not emphasise the value of education to their children. Some of them grow up illiterate since they were born to parents who couldn't read or write. This is particularly true in rural regions, where a large portion of the elderly population lacks a formal education.
5. **Lack of awareness:** - The degree of illiteracy may be high in certain isolated locations, and there are many individuals who do not comprehend why it is crucial for them to attend school. Urban areas have a lower percentage of illiterates than rural ones. People who live in cities are more conscious of the need to eradicate the illiteracy issue and the difficulties brought on by a lack of education. Additionally, it compares the societal advantages of literacy to those who resided in rural regions.
6. **Inexpensive educational facilities:** - Many people in rural regions lack access to schooling and may continue to be illiterate. They could be many miles from their home country from the local school. Many of them opt to stay home rather than taking the tiresome road of regularly trekking vast distances simply to get to school. The greater percentage of illiteracy in rural and isolated locations is a result of the lack of access to educational institutions in these areas.

Government's initiatives for making people literate:-

*** For education and literacy**

[The National Education Policy, 2020 seeks to "make India a universal knowledge superpower" by enacting several improvements from the secondary to the post-secondary levels.] 2

- **Samagra Shiksha:** This comprehensive programme covers kindergarten through class XII and is designed to guarantee inclusive and equitable quality education at all stages of schooling.
- **Mid-Day Meal Programme:** Under this programme, any student in classes I through VIII between the ages of six and fourteen who enrolls in the school is entitled to daily, free, hot, nutrient-rich meals, excluding school vacations.

*** For digital literacy -**

- The Digital India Programme unifies several current programmes by reorganising, refocusing, and then implementing them in a coordinated fashion.
- Pradhan Mantri Gramin Digital Saksharta Abhiyan: This is one of the nation's biggest projects to promote digital literacy among the populace.
- The National Digital Literacy Mission seeks to equip at least one member of each family with essential digital literacy abilities.
- The Bharat Net Programme seeks to install an optical fibre network throughout every GramPanchayat.

Solutions to the illiteracy issue: -

1. **Free education** - By encouraging more individuals to attend school, the government's free education programmes in schools, colleges, and universities can significantly lower the rate of illiteracy in a nation. Because some individuals choose not to go to school

because they cannot afford the fees, providing free education may boost enrollment and, as a result, lower societal illiteracy rates.

2. **Creating awareness** - People can better comprehend the necessity for education by raising awareness of its significance. Non-governmental organisations, governmental bodies, and other interested parties should implement concerted efforts to raise public awareness and lower the number of persons who are illiterate.
3. **Grants:** By providing grants, subsidies, and scholarships, you may lessen the financial strain that parents and students must suffer when paying for their children's education. Due to the lack of school costs, it would enable students to learn without having to stop their studies. In addition, parents would direct the funds that would have gone towards school fees into other income-producing endeavours. For people who live in poverty, the expense of supporting school may prove to be too expensive.
4. **Digitization:** Since we live in an information and technology-driven age, developing digital platforms for reading and learning can aid in lowering the rate of illiteracy among the general population. It can also aid in addressing the issue of the lack of educational facilities. For those who reside distant from metropolitan centres to increase their knowledge base and level of awareness, digital libraries might be a valuable resource.
5. **Less expensive education:** Although education offers benefits, it is incredibly expensive to finance. The majority of graduates often exit school with sizable student loan debt. It makes investing and saving challenging. In many countries, the expense of higher education has been a significant political and social concern. The government can make it

simpler for people to complete their education at the greatest level feasible by cutting the expense of schooling.

Government's role in eradicating illiteracy in India: -

Since our nation's independence, the government has been attempting to eradicate poverty through a variety of programmes. Still, there is a need to motivate individuals to continue their studies. The government and several NGOs have been attempting to find a solution to the apparently unsolvable issue of eliminating illiteracy in India for both adults and children. The fundamental financial literacy computer programmes for teaching people how to read and write. NGOs encourage individuals to enrol in night programmes and studies and offer the necessary resources. The government is also providing literary funding and concentrating only on enhancing the reading and writing skills of youngsters and adults.

The Supreme Court ruled in 1993 that children had a fundamental right to free public education. The 83rd Amendment to the Constitution, passed in 2000, established the "Right to Education," which was how the activity was carried out. Despite this, the nation was still unable to give children up to the age of fourteen with free and required schooling. The endeavour is still ongoing as the government works to inspire parents and educate kids by creating new structures and advancements in educational delivery. The necessity of education for everyone is stated in the Indian Constitution. As a result, it has established a number of regulations that guarantee India's educational rights are implemented correctly and effectively.

Some of the provisions are:-

- [Education for a group of Minorities: Article 30 of the Constitution provides all minorities have the right to set and administer institutions of their preference.] 3
- [Free and Compulsory Education: Article 41, 45, and 46 of the Directive Principles of State Policy of the Constitution instructs the state to ensure that all citizens must receive free education] 4
- Equality of Opportunity in Educational Institutions: The fundamental right of equality clearly signifies that in the eyes of the law, there can be no discrimination based on caste, status, sex, class, or creed. Equal opportunities must be provided to everyone in a country.
- [Article 21 (A) as the fundamental right: The new amendment was brought to provide free and mandatory education to all children between the age of 6 to 14 years; this is made as to the fundamental right] 5
- Education for Weaker Sections: Article 15 and 46 of the Constitution also safeguard the educational interests of the weaker sections of society.

Research methodology: -

The research methodology for this research paper is descriptive. At the primary stage of the research work, primary sources related to illiteracy and its measures to eradicate it are consulted which helps in tracking the origin of illiteracy and its measures to eradicate it. Work of foreign articles, newspapers, journals, magazines oral research etc. are also a part of this endeavour. Coming into the final stage of the research, all the information and facts collected during the primary stage are carefully analysed, compared and interpreted.

Here I applied analytical, comparative and doctrinal methods to find out the most reliable facts, their viability, credibility, discrepancy and infirmity if any exist. It is very difficult to analyse and compare all the existing material on this particular topic, however, every honest possible effort is made to collect appropriate information, data and material as possible on the subject for the preparation of this research article.

Conclusion: -

The worth of education can't be undervalued. Many individuals like to think about it just as a cycle to acquire the abilities and skill important for the gig market. Despite the fact that schooling gives an individual an upper hand in the gig market, that isn't all that it does. Going to class assumes a significant part in the psychological as well as friendly improvement of an individual. The examples learned and the encounters that an individual goes through while in school get ready the person in question for life in the public eye. One can master critical thinking abilities and foster the social insight important to defeat day to day existence challenges. Ignorance, thusly, has no room in current culture. The more the quantity of individuals who have gone to class, the better the local area. Everybody ought to try to be instructed and gain information on account of the significant advantages of being proficient.

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